

WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER FOR AN EYE IMPLANT

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ABSTRACT

Active medical implants need electrical energy and a wireless power supply is often desirable. Several possible technologies for wireless power transfer are already available to developers of medical devices. If the focus is on the most widespread technologies, the spectrum ranges from electromagnetic solutions in the low-frequency kHz to the high-frequency GHz range. In this paper we show for an eye implant that a conventional solution in the near field using magnetic coupling at 13.56 MHz, and a customized solution in the far field at 900 MHz can be used. A proof-of-concept for measuring the eye pressure using the near field magnetic coupling was confirmed with a pre-clinical study.

KEYWORDS: smart implants, wireless power transfer, eye implant, predictive health

INTRODUCTION

Neurostimulators or cochlear implants are active medical implants and need electrical energy. A wireless power supply is often desirable for this. Surgery to replace batteries, for example, will then not be necessary anymore - and every intervention that can be done without surgery reduces the risk of infection.

On an example of an eye implant, we show which technologies for wireless power transfer are available today and how the most suitable one can be chosen.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the development of the wireless power transfer solution, we used simulation methods as well as testing in the high-frequency laboratory. For the simulation, a combination of self-developed and commercial simulation tools came into use to precisely represent the electromagnetic boundary conditions, including absorption in the surrounding tissue.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We developed a wireless power link for an electronic eye implant for continuous measurement of the intraocular pressure. Simulations showed that two variants were possible: a conventional solution in the near field using magnetic coupling at 13.56 MHz, and a customized solution in the far field at 900 MHz.

A pre-clinical study with implants operating in the near field at 13.56 MHz was successfully completed and in-vitro testing confirmed the simulation results, which indicated a range of up to 1m for wireless power transfer at 900 MHz. But there was another argument in favor of the latter solution: Because of the dielectric properties of the surrounding tissue, a UHF antenna at 900 MHz can be implemented with significantly smaller dimensions than an antenna in air. With proper design methods, it was even possible to place the antenna on the non-optical surface of an intraocular lens.

Fig. 1: Intra-ocular lens with antenna (in blue), simulation model of an anatomical eye.

Fig. 2: Radiation characteristics of the Ultra High-Frequency antenna (simulation result).

CONCLUSIONS

Over the past few years, we have developed various wireless power and data links for medical applications that work in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 2.5 GHz. Depending on the area of application, standard technologies such as NFC (13.56 MHz) or Bluetooth (2.4 GHz) can be employed. However, if the application-specific needs cannot be met with standard technologies, proprietary developments are used to close this gap.

There are already implants available on the market that are charged via an external wireless link, such products are in the field of continuous glucose monitoring or neuromodulation. More of such “smart” implants will be brought to the market to address unmet clinical needs with the new technologies available. Smart implants will have the potential to support the shift towards a more predictive, data driven health care approach.

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